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IMPROVING SHOPPING MALL REVENUE BY REAL TIME CUSTOMIZED DIGITAL COUPON ISSUANCE

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ABSTRACT

With the development of big data and deep learning technology, big data and deep learning technology have also been applied to the marketing field, which was a part of business administration. Customer churn management is one of the most important areas of marketing. In this paper, we proposed a method to prevent customer churn and increase purchase conversion rate by issuing customized discount coupons to customers with high churn rate based on big data in real time. After segmenting customer segments with two-dimensional segment analysis, a real-time churn rate estimation model based on clickstream data was generated for each segment. After that, we issued customized coupons to our customers. Finally, we tested the conversion rate and sales growth. A two-dimensional cluster analysis-based churn rate estimation combined with a recommendation system was found to be significantly more useful than the respective simple models. Using this proposed model, it is possible to increase

sales by automatically estimating the customer's churn probability and shopping propensity without the burden of marketing costs in the online shopping mall.

INTRODUCTION

With the development of big data and deep learning technology, big data and deep learning technology have also been applied to the marketing field, which was a part of management. Also, growth in internet adoption has made digital coupons a popular promotional tool [1]. Customized digital coupon issuance is a very important topic in online commerce. This is because maintaining existing customers is a more important business issue than acquiring new customers [2]. Also, retaining existing customers is much more economically advantageous than acquiring new customers [3]. In fact, the acquisition cost of new customers is known to be five to six times higher than the maintenance cost of existing customers [4]. Companies that have effectively managed customer churn by improving customer retention are known to have a positive effect not only on the

company's profitability but also on improving brand image by improving customer satisfaction. Customized coupon issuance research has traditionally been active in highly competitive and urgent sectors such as telecommunications, finance, distribution, and game industries, and has focused mainly on developing predictive models using machine learning and artificial intelligence technology [6]. Also, recently, AI-based marketing using big data analysis and deep learning is emerging. Such AI-driven targeting can save huge amounts of marketing costs and raise online sales provided that the targeting model succeeds in estimating customer responsiveness accurately [7]. In particular, in the case of online shopping malls, the average purchase conversion rate is around 2%. Online shopping malls have the advantage of being easily accessed through the PC web or mobile web, but on the contrary, this advantage can be a disadvantage that it is easy to see and leave quickly.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Machine learning-based marketing research has been actively conducted in the fields of customer segmentation, customer churn prediction, and personalized recommendation. With the emergence of online digital marketing, related research is

increasing further due to the real-time nature of online and the ease of accessing data

A. CUSTOMER SEGMENTATION STUDY

Customer segmentation is a starting point for marketing research. After grouping customers based on the characteristics of homogeneous customers, marketing strategies for each target segment can be done. Customer segmentation should not end in segmentation, but should be accompanied with subsequent marketing strategies. Companies that use customer segmentation techniques perform better by building differentiated and efficient marketing for each segment of customers. In addition, companies can gain a deeper understanding of customer preferences and requirements. Among various customer segmentation techniques, RFM methods are the most classical yet universally utilized methods

B. FORECAST CUSTOMER CHURN

The prediction and prevention of customer churn have always been studied as a key issue in loyalty management. The reason why companies are concerned with churn prediction is of two issues: the first reason is that a large number of customer churn affect the reputation and reliability of service providers. The second reason is that

attaining a new customer costs five to six times than retaining an old customer. It is necessary to develop a churn prediction model that should catch deviating from normal purchase pattern [22]. Researches on customer churn are mainly based on machine learning techniques rather than empirical studies through hypothesis verification [23]. Predicting churning customers fall under the classification problem where the given customer is classified as either churn or non-churn. Reference [24] proposed a framework for proactive detection of customer churn based on support vector machine and a hybrid recommendation strategy

C. PERSONALIZED RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM

The personalized recommendation is one of the most actively conducted machine learning-based marketing research topics. In the past, personalized recommendation researches were mainly conducted using association analysis or purchase probability estimation for individual products [27]. However, in recent, collaborative filtering applied to recommended services such as Amazon and Netflix and contentbased techniques are the leading trend within the research field. Recently, hybrid methods or deep learning-based research combining various auxiliary processing techniques has

also been active [28]. Design of recommendation system depends on the objective of the system. Therefore, there exist a wide variety of techniques used in the recommendation system. Content-based and collaborative filtering systems are mostly used [29].

D. APPLICATION OF DEEP LEARNING IN VARIOUS FIELDS

Advances in deep learning have solved many problems using deep learning in many industries. The method using deep learning was applied to the battery industry example. Reference [40] proposed deep learning-based prognostic method for lithium-ion batteries with on-line validation. Also, it applied machinery fault field. Reference [41] proposed an adversarial multi-classifier optimization method for crossdomain fault diagnosis based on deep learning. There are also cases where deep learning has been applied in the medical field. Reference [42] proposed a method to find out the name of a disease through the clinical note of patients using deep learning. Reference [43] proposed a method for predicting the deterioration of dementia based on medical records. In addition, deep learning was applied in the field of semantic analysis, which plays the biggest role in creating chatbots. Reference [44] proposed a method to measure the

similarity between two sentences using deep learning

EXISTING SYSTEM

Customer segmentation is a starting point for marketing research. After grouping customers based on the characteristics of homogeneous customers, marketing strategies for each target segment can be done. Customer segmentation should not end in segmentation, but should be accompanied with subsequent marketing strategies. Companies that use customer segmentation techniques perform better by building differentiated and efficient marketing for each segment of customers. In addition, companies can gain a deeper understanding of customer preferences and requirements. Among various customer segmentation techniques, RFM methods are the most classical yet universally utilized methods. The RFM splits the purchasing behavior into three dimensions and scores each dimension. R is the last time since the last purchase, F is the total frequency of purchase, and M is the total purchase amount. The scores are calculated for each of the three dimensions. Subsequently, it constructs segments according to three dimensional classes [15], [16], [17], [18]. Along with traditional RFM methods, a lot of customer segmentation researches using machine

learning have been conducted recently. When clustering using multiple variables, dimensionality reduction is often done. A representative dimensionality reduction technique using deep learning is the autoencoder. A typical example is the sequential method of applying cluster analysis after dimensionality reduction using an autoencoder [19]. Alternatively, modeling can combine dimensionality and clustering at the same time [20], [21]. The prediction and prevention of customer churn have always been studied as a key issue in loyalty management.

DISADVANTAGES

- The complexity of data: Most of the existing machine learning models must be able to accurately interpret large and complex datasets to detect Improving Shopping Mall Revenue.
- Data availability: Most machine learning models require large amounts of data to create accurate predictions. If data is unavailable in sufficient quantities, then model accuracy may suffer.
- Incorrect labeling: The existing machine learning models are only as accurate as the data trained using the input dataset. If the data has been incorrectly labeled, the model cannot make accurate predictions.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this study, applying deep learning techniques to real-time click stream data,

we find customers with high chance of churning rates and issue a coupon that suits customers' preferences. This study has the following significance: First, we segmented the customer and develop a suitable model for customer churn prediction for each segmentation. Second, we made a clickstream-based real-time customer churn risk prediction model using deep learning models. Third, we improved the actual conversion rate by issuing customized coupons in real shopping mall website. Unlike other studies, the scientific contribution of this study was to analyze customers in real time using data collected in real time as well as going through three steps to prevent customer churn. Also, we applied our model to the actual shopping mall, demonstrating the economic effectiveness and efficiency of the three steps of our model.

Advantages

The proposed system generated RNN-based churn estimation models for each customer segment resulted from two-dimensional customer segmentation. After that, we issued customized product category coupons to customers who are at high risk of churn. Hybrid recommendation system is utilized for customized coupon issuance.

Modules

Service Provider

In this module, the Service Provider has to login by using valid user name and password. After login successful he can do some operations such as Train & Test Data Sets, View Trained and Tested Accuracy in Bar Chart, View Trained and Tested Accuracy Results, View Prediction Of Shopping Mall Revenue Type, View Shopping Mall Revenue Prediction Type Ratio, Download Predicted Data Sets, View Shopping Mall Revenue Prediction Type Ratio Results, View All Remote User

View and Authorize Users

In this module, the admin can view the list of users who all registered. In this, the admin can view the user's details

such as, user name, email, address and admin authorizes the users.

Remote User

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before doing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user will do some operations like REGISTER AND LOGIN Predict Shopping Mall Revenue Prediction Type, VIEW YOUR PROFILE.

ALGORITHMS

DECISION TREE CLASSIFICATION ALGORITHM

- Decision Tree is a **Supervised learning technique** that can be used for both classification and Regression problems, but mostly it

is preferred for solving Classification problems. It is a tree-structured classifier, where **internal nodes represent the features of a dataset, branches represent the decision rules and each leaf node represents the outcome.**

- In a Decision tree, there are two nodes, which are the **Decision Node** and **Leaf Node**. Decision nodes are used to make any decision and have multiple branches, whereas Leaf nodes are the output of those decisions and do not contain any further branches.
- The decisions or the test are performed on the basis of features of the given dataset.
- *It is a graphical representation for getting all the possible solutions to a problem/decision based on given conditions.*
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K-NEAREST NEIGHBOR(KNN) ALGORITHM FOR MACHINE LEARNING

- K-Nearest Neighbour is one of the simplest Machine Learning algorithms based on Supervised Learning technique.

- K-NN algorithm assumes the similarity between the new case/data and available cases and put the new case into the category that is most similar to the available categories.
- K-NN algorithm stores all the available data and classifies a new data point based on the similarity. This means when new data appears then it can be easily classified into a well suite category by using K- NN algorithm.
- K-NN algorithm can be used for Regression as well as for Classification but mostly it is used for the Classification problems.
- K-NN is a **non-parametric algorithm**, which means it does not make any assumption on underlying data.
- It is also called a **lazy learner algorithm** because it does not learn from the training set immediately instead it stores the dataset and at the time of classification, it performs an action on the dataset.

CONCLUSION

We identified previous e-commerce marketing approaches to derive user behavior prediction. A deep learning method for real time customer churn

prediction showed an appropriate result. We applied our research to online shopping mall to raise conversion rate and sales. To check whether our experiment carry out monetary value, we developed a framework to measure the sales amount when used with segment model and personalized recommended digital coupon. We found that our model (scenario1) shows the best results. We found it is suitable for e-commerce online shopping mall to raise conversion rate and sales. Our study empirically showed that marketing, which was a field of management, could be solved more efficiently and quickly by applying big data and deep learning technology.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Naval and N. Pandey, "What makes a consumer redeem digital coupons? Behavioral insights from grounded theory approach," *J. Promotion Manage.*, vol. 28, no. 3, pp. 205–238, 2021.

- [2] C. Hung and C. F. Tsai, "Market segmentation based on hierarchical selforganizing map for markets of multimedia on demand," *Expert Syst. With Appl.*, vol. 34, pp. 780–787, Jan. 2008.
- [3] G. Nie, "Finding the hidden pattern of credit card holder's churn: A case of China," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Comput. Sci.* Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2009, pp. 561–569.
- [4] A. D. Athanassopoulos, "Customer satisfaction cues to support market segmentation and explain switching behavior," *J. Bus. Res.*, vol. 47, no. 3, pp. 191–207, Mar. 2000.
- [5] C. Hung and C. F. Tsai, "Market segmentation based on hierarchical selforganizing map for markets of multimedia on demand," *Expert Syst. With Appl.*, vol. 34, pp. 780–787, Jan. 2008.
- [6] H.-S. Kim and H. Seung-Woo, "A two-dimensional customer loyalty segment-based customer churn prediction methodology," *Intell. Inf. Res.*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 111–126, 2020.
- [7] R. M. Gubela, S. Lessmann, and S. Jaroszewicz, "Response transformation and profit decomposition for revenue uplift modeling," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, vol. 283, no. 2, pp. 647–661, Jun. 2020.
- [8] M.-S. Chang, H. Kim, and Joong, "A customer segmentation scheme base on big data in a bank," *J. Digit. Contents Soc.*, vol. 19, no. 1, pp. 85–91, 2018.
- [9] N. Chang, "Improving the effectiveness of customer classification models: A pre-segmentation approach," *Inf. Syst. Rev.*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 23–40, 2005.
- [10] C.-F. Tsai and Y.-H. Lu, "Customer churn prediction by hybrid neural networks," *Expert Syst. Appl.*, vol. 36, no. 10, pp. 12547–12553, Dec. 2009.
- [12] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Design of a Dual Doping Less Double Gate Tfet and Its Material Optimization Analysis on a 6t Sram Cells."
- [13] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Low power process, voltage, and temperature (PVT) variations aware improved tunnel FET on 6T SRAM cells." *Sustainable Computing: Informatics and Systems* 21 (2019): 143-153.
- [14] Reddy, K. Niranjana, and P. V. Y. Jayasree. "Survey on improvement of PVT aware variations in tunnel FET on SRAM cells." In *2017 International Conference on Current Trends in Computer, Electrical, Electronics and Communication (CTCEEC)*, pp. 703-705. IEEE, 2017
- [15] Karne, R. K. ., & Sreeja, T. K. . (2023). PMLC- Predictions of Mobility and Transmission in a Lane-Based Cluster VANET Validated on Machine Learning. *International Journal on Recent and Innovation Trends in Computing and Communication*, 11(5s), 477–

483.

<https://doi.org/10.17762/ijritcc.v11i5s.7109>

[16] Radha Krishna Karne and Dr. T. K. Sreeja (2022), A Novel Approach for Dynamic Stable Clustering in VANET Using Deep Learning (LSTM) Model. IJEER 10(4), 1092-1098. DOI: 10.37391/IJEER.100454.

[17] Reddy, Kallem Niranjan, and Pappu Venkata Yasoda Jayasree. "Low Power Strain and Dimension Aware SRAM Cell Design Using a New Tunnel FET and Domino Independent Logic." *International Journal of Intelligent Engineering & Systems* 11, no. 4 (2018).

[18] P. A. Sarvari, A. Ustundag, and H. Takci, "Performance evaluation of different customer segmentation approaches based on RFM and demographics analysis," *Kybernetes*, vol. 45, no. 7, pp. 1129–1157, Aug. 2016.

[19] F. Tian, "Learning deep representations for graph clustering," in *Proc. AAAI Conf. Artif. Intell.*, 2014, pp. 1293–1299.

[20] J. Girshick and R. Farhadi, "Unsupervised deep embedding for clustering analysis," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Mach. Learn.*, 2016, pp. 478–487.

[21] K. Tian, S. Zhou, and J. Guan, "Deepcluster: A general clustering framework based on deep learning," in *Proc. Joint Eur. Conf. Mach. Learn. Knowl. Discovery Databases*. Cham, Switzerland: Springer, 2017, pp. 809–825.

[22] S. Oh, E. Lee, J. Woo, and H. K. Kim, "Constructing and evaluating a churn prediction model using classification of user types in MMORPG," *KIISE Trans. Comput. Practices*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 220–226, May 2018.

[23] J. Kawale, A. Pal, and J. Srivastava, "Churn prediction in MMORPGs: A social influence based approach," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Comput. Sci. Eng.*, 2009, pp. 423–428.

[24] S. Renjith, "B2C E-Commerce customer churn management: Churn detection using support vector machine and personalized retention using hybrid recommendations," *Int. J. Future Revolution Comput. Sci. Commun. Eng.*, vol. 3, no. 11, pp. 34–39, 2017.

[25] B. Mishachandar and K. A. Kumar, "Predicting customer churn using targeted proactive retention," *Int. J. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 7, no. 2, p. 69, Aug. 2018.